

ISic3421

I.Sicily inscription 3421

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object

architrave

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Theatre

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 644816

Bibliography

Manganaro, G. 1961. Ricerche di epigrafia siceliota. I. Per la storia del culto delle divinità orientali in Sicilia. *Siculorum Gymnasium*. 14: 175-198. At 195 fig.20
Wilson, R.J.A. 1996. La topografia della Catania romana. Problemi e prospettive. In Gentile, B.(eds.), *Catania Antica. Atti del Convegno della S.I.S.A.C. (Catania 23-24 maggio 1992)*. Pisa. pp. 149-173. At 161 n.35

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